

LEARNING OF FOREIGN LANGUAGES IN THE PANDEMIC PERIOD

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Abstract. *This article is devoted to the educational problems during the pandemic Covid-19 period. The author observed some factors which influence the learning process. Considered some modern methodologies for teaching foreign languages through distance. The authors present the advantages and disadvantages of distance learning of foreign languages.*

Keywords: *education, distance learning, communication, learning foreign languages, approach, the modern methodologies, flipped classroom, ESL classes, advantages, disadvantages.*

The pandemic of Covid-19 and the quarantine regime influenced everyday life and people's labor activity at the same time it changed traditional education processes all over the world. It was urgently necessary to provide students with knowledge. It was distance education in these conditions that played the role of a lifesaver. Using Distance Education in Uzbekistan in the Covid-19 pandemic provides applying online or distance learning in the system of education and the perspectives of such development are analyzed. [12]

President Shavkat Mirziyoyev in his Decree on the "State Program for the Implementation of the Action Strategy" instructed to introduce of distance education in universities. The Ministry of Higher and Secondary Specialized Education should ensure by April 1, 2020, that conditions are created for organizing distance learning at the universities of Uzbekistan. It is necessary to define the order to create a software-hardware complex and provide all necessary equipment for the introduction of distance learning in the educational process of specified higher educational institutions. Auditorium lessons traditionally exist in three types: verbal, nonverbal, and written. Verbal communication means anything that a teacher or student speaks aloud. Nonverbal communication is when we use body language instead of colloquial. Written communication is the writing process of special topics, such as reports, comments, or student assignments. Teachers and students interact with one another in many different contexts and use all three of these types of communication. Teacher/class communication exists when a teacher communicates with his entire class. Colloquial communication exists when a teacher tells students the information they need to know. For example, if a teacher asks a student to "stop talking," this is a direct form of verbal communication.

There are some methods for teachers to contact nonverbally with their students, such as through their posture, gestures, etc. to their students. Instead of telling a student to stop talking, a teacher could use nonverbal communication by moving toward the disruptive student's desk. Not only does the disruptive student receive the message, but other students in the class who observe the intervention receive it as well. Written instructions for an assignment are given by the teacher to the whole class. Teacher/student is an action when a teacher interacts directly with one student. While a teacher interacts with her/his students mostly in front of the whole class, it can be difficult to distinguish teacher/student communication from teacher/class communication. Teacher/student

communication demands the teacher act one-on-one with a student, such as in a conference during class activities, before or after class. This type of communication is useful for teachers who want to connect by a private message, such as a talk about bad behavior or about taking more of a leadership role in class.

Student/teacher communication is also done between a student and the teacher, but this time it is the student who starts the conversation himself. Also, this process can go on during whole-class activity. For example, a student who asks a teacher a question during class discussion attracts student/teacher communication because it is a single student communicating with only the teacher. The goal to reverse the situation constitutes teacher/class communication and not a teacher/student is that the teacher's actions and messages are towered the whole class while the student's questions here are only directed at the teacher. When students write emails to their teacher on assignments, this provides a written form of student/teacher communication.

Student/student communication occurs when two or more students interact with one another. Successful whole-class discussion stimulates student/student communication because students should talk to each other and not just to the teacher. Two students may disagree and talk back and forth to each other during such discussions. Student/student communication also occurs when students work in groups or pairs to complete assignments.

Student/class communication exists when a student or group of students address messages to the class. Whole-class activity can also stimulate this type of communication. For example, if a student asks the class a question during a discussion, the student's message is given to the whole class. Individual or group presentations also make up student/class communication, and it is this type of communication which students do not like. Nonverbal communication often includes fidgeting or paying less attention. [1]

Media literacy education is a field that is fraught with disagreement over definitions, approaches, principles, and purposes, but teaching media literacy is arguably needed now more than ever before, especially for ESL and EFL students. From the research available, it appears as though many ESL and EFL students are not taught media literacy in their home countries. Additionally, much of the research that does exist in regard to teaching media literacy to ESL and EFL students focuses on forms of media that are no longer relevant to most learners. Since ESL and EFL teachers support the development of their students' English-language skills, it is justifiable that at least some of the responsibility of media literacy education should fall on their shoulders. The widespread transition to virtual learning as a result of COVID-19 presents a unique opportunity for ESL and EFL teachers to teach media literacy to their students. However, because this period also presents numerous challenges to the public's collective media literacy skills, it is imperative that teachers integrate media literacy education into their pedagogy. [6]

From the 2020/2021 academic year till January 1, 2021, due to the timetable The Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan, taking into account the results of the experiment, submitted the implementation of distance education in the higher education system.

In a pandemic, the learning process is based on distance technologies students from 88 educational institutions are covered by online classes. This new educational style provides uninterrupted learning. Taking such a decision the authorities should guarantee the quality of distance education. The Internet speed, equipment for conducting e-learning and etc. In its term in the classroom, a teacher can be dynamic and learners can move around, providing a qualified process of the lessons. In the digital classroom, this isn't possible, so a teacher needs to plan to fill

every minute of the lesson and to make sure there is a good choice of activities and materials to choose the appropriate materials for classes and being done by students independently. Even with a simple platform that doesn't have a lot of important terms, it's important to be able to use it confidently so that you can focus on delivering lessons and not the technology. Get to know your platform well by watching video tutorials or reading. Then, practice using the platform by asking friends, family, or colleagues to play the student or by offering a student a free lesson. If you do the latter, make it clear that there may be technical problems. [10]

Now the challenge is the quality of the completion of the academic year. Taking into account the experience of foreign countries and the current situation, it is planned to conduct final exams at universities in an online form. Despite this the teachers conduct special syllabuses and selected and download special adopted materials for modules, they consist of lesson materials, additional materials, listening, presentation on the theme, and video after learning all these materials students fulfill the home tasks of each unit, and submit them on the module platform.

The definition of e-learning is this: distance learning is improved opportunities in knowledge and/or behaviors as a result of mediated experiences that are constrained by time and/or distance such that the learner does not share the same situation with what's being learned. From this definition of distance learning flows the definition of distance education. Distance education is formalized instructional learning where the time/geographic situation constrains learning by requiring synchronous person-to-person interaction. [3]

We believe that by considering the constraints present in each type of learning, we level the playing field for researching differences between the traditional, in-person education and distance education. We propose that traditional learning and distance learning become co-equal, each has its affordances and each has its constraints, which should be enumerated by research. Our belief runs counter to the prevailing concept that distance education is the weak stepchild of in-person education. A focus on constraints may release us from repeatedly proving the null hypothesis, that distance education is not different from in-person education. Clearly, there may even be times when distance education proves superior. Distance education has clear affordances that in-person education does not, permitting, for example, extended time for reflection before answering, use of distributed resources without interrupting the flow of discussion or class presentations, constant recording of many interactions (clusters, bulletin boards, and e-mail) for research and marking purposes. Thus, we propose that the affordances of distance education be compared to the affordances of in-person education and the constraints of distance education be compared to the constraints of in-person education, providing a level playing field for research.

Flipped Classroom

One of the modern approaches which gained more popularity in last years, Flipped Classroom is a pedagogical approach in which the traditional elements of the lesson taught by the teacher are reversed – the primary educational materials are studied by the students at home and, then, worked on in the classroom (zoom) in our case.[9] The main objective of this methodology is to optimize time in class by dedicating it, for example, to meet the special needs of each individual student, develop cooperative projects or work on specific tasks. This is an example task. Students get the task by module platform they should read the information about the disease (signs or symptoms) and decide what kind of illness it is. During the Zoom classes, they share their prognosis together with the group. The task can be given as an individual so for group work as well.

Students should read the eleven descriptions given and using their vocabulary match the diagnosis through symptoms. (here they need not only their knowledge of English but apply medical) [2]

1. A disorder of the nervous system in which there are convulsions and loss of consciousness due to disordered discharge of cerebral neurons.
2. A condition where tissues die and decay, as a result of bacterial action, because the blood supply has been lost through injury or disease of the artery.
3. A condition where the lens of the eye gradually becomes hard and opaque.
4. A progressive nervous disorder without a known cause which is a type of Parkinsonism, the main symptoms of which are trembling hands, a slow shuffling walk and difficulty in speaking.
5. An infectious disease in which infected lumps form in the tissue. Its commonest form is infection of the lungs, causing patients to lose weight, cough blood and have a fever. It is caught by breathing in germs or by eating contaminated food, especially unpasteurized milk.
6. A hereditary disease in which there is malfunction of the exocrine glands such as the pancreas, in particular those which secrete mucus, causing respiratory difficulties, male infertility and malabsorption of food from the gastrointestinal tract.
7. A progressive disease of the liver, often associated with alcoholism, in which healthy cells are replaced by scar tissue.
8. A serious, infectious disease of children. Its first symptoms are a sore throat, followed by a slight fever, rapid pulse and swelling of the glands in the neck. A fibrous growth like a membrane forms in the throat and can close the air passages. The disease is often fatal, either because the patient is asphyxiated or because the heart becomes fatally weakened.
9. A disorder of the brain, mainly due to brain damage occurring before birth, or due to lack of oxygen during birth. The patient may have bad coordination of muscular movements, impaired speech, hearing, and sight, and sometimes mental retardation.
10. Inflammation of the membrane lining the intestines and the stomach, caused by a viral infection and resulting in diarrhea and vomiting.

These words are all used to talk about illnesses: their symptoms and effects. Students should tick the ones they understand after reading the descriptions below they should match them to the names of the illnesses in the box.

Symptoms & common illnesses [4]

- | | | |
|----------------------|-----------------|----------------|
| 1. allergic reaction | 6. inflammation | 11. resistance |
| 2. blister | 7. itchy | 12. runny nose |
| 3. cough | 8. malformation | 13. sneeze |
| 4. fever | 9. malaise | 14. spot |
| 5. infectious | 10. rash | 15. swelling |

1. An infectious disease of the upper respiratory tract with fever and muscular aches, which is transmitted by a virus and can occur in epidemics.

2. A common infectious viral disease of children, with mild fever, swollen lymph nodes and a rash. It can cause stillbirth or malformation of an unborn baby if the mother catches the disease while pregnant.

3. An illness, with inflammation of the nasal passages, in which someone sneezes and coughs and has a blocked and running nose.

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4. An infectious disease of children, caused by the herpes virus and characterized by fever and red spots which turn into itchy blisters.
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5. An infectious disease of children where the body is covered with a red rash. It can weaken the body's resistance to other diseases, especially bronchitis and ear infections. If caught by an adult it can be very serious.
.....

6. An infectious disease of children, with fever and swellings in the salivary glands, caused by a paramyxovirus.
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7. An infectious disease affecting the bronchial tubes, common in children and sometimes very serious. The patient coughs very badly and makes a characteristic 'whoop' when inhaling after a coughing fit.
.....

8. Inflammation in the nose and eyes caused by an allergic reaction to plant pollen, mold spores, dust mites, or animal hair.
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allergic rhinitis

coryza

infectious parotitis

influenza

pertussis

rubella

rubeola

varicella

Advantages:

Students can interact with a facilitator in real-time and get instant feedback from instructors. They may be more motivated to ask questions or to take part in discussions. The main advantage of distance learning is that it presents students with a flexible alternative to traditional classroom-based education. It gives students greater access to education. Students, who are unable to attend classes due to disabilities, or due to family responsibilities, may be able to further their studies via distance learning. At the same time, it is especially important to develop innovative tasks for students, since the main purpose of such tasks is to activate the student's regular mental activity at the initiation stage. Modern approaches to teaching English as a foreign language are based on the emotional memory of the student, on the formation of communicative and professional competence, and on the regular training of the student's creative activity. It is more affordable. Students can save money by not having to travel to classes.

It gives students the option to work and study at the same time. Because distance learning students are free to study according to their own schedules, they can easily fit in their studies around their work commitments. It allows students to study at their own pace. Students won't be under pressure to keep up with the rest of the class, and they won't be held back by slower students. They can also choose how much time to spend on each section of the course material. [5]

Disadvantages of distance learning are:

Students will have less flexibility, as they will have to be available to attend classes by the timetable.

They will need to have access to the relevant technology (which may be expensive).

Also will need to be comfortable using the relevant technology, and will need to be more self-disciplined to study on your own and stick to your study schedule.

Have fewer opportunities for interaction with other students, and have to wait longer for feedback from their instructors.

Academic support is given to students through various channels, including telephone, post, email, and instant messaging programs.

Students are not limited to studying courses that are offered by academic institutions in their geographical areas. [5]

It helps students to develop valuable skills. Students will be able to improve their self-discipline, sense of responsibility, time management, and independent thinking skills by studying largely on their own via distance learning.

It presents students with fewer distractions. While the social aspect of campus life often distracts students from their studies, distance learning makes it easier for students to remain focused.

Distance learning is a great opportunity for those who want to further their studies, but are unable to attend classes on a regular basis. However, distance learning is not the right choice for everyone – it is best suited to self-disciplined and self-motivated people.

It is also good for people who have a disability that makes it difficult to attend classes.

It is convenient for those with family responsibilities preventing them from attending classes.

When students live far away from campus or have problems with getting transport to campus.

There is often minimal interaction with other students. However, students may be able to interact online, or they may decide to form their own study groups.

It requires high levels of self-discipline. In most cases, there won't be anyone checking up on students to make sure that they get through their work on time. [7]

In conclusion, we can say in this period of the Covid-19 pandemic distance learning is a reliable transfer of knowledge.

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